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THE RELEVANCE OF MBIAM AS A VERITABLE TOOL IN REGULATING CRIME IN TRADITIONAL ANNANG LAND

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ABSTRACT

The persistent increase and frightening rate of criminal and corrupt practices that have engulfed the contemporary Annang society is a cause for serious concern. This stands in stark contrast to the past, when traditional approaches and strategies were employed to combat crime. It may be argued that the sophisticated weaponry employed by security personnel lately has not had a major impact on crime reduction; this is because of the manifestation of social disarray in the normative system of the Annang people. In view of the above, this work aimed to retrospectively x-ray Mbiam as a traditional method of crime control in pre-colonial Annang society with a view to highlighting that this method can be applied contemporarily to mitigate the meteoric rise in crime in Annang land, since the modern or Western methods have not dealt with crime significantly. The study deployed a descriptive research technique, with data drawn from in-depth interviews with the custodians of the Annang traditions in addition to consultation of other related secondary sources. The findings of the study revealed that although Mbiam was pivotal in crime control in pre-colonial Annang land, it has been drastically relegated to nothingness in the contemporary Annang society via the instrumentality of the influence of western culture and civilization. The work suggests an integration of Mbiam into the Western style or system of crime control to ensure optimal performance and effectiveness in curbing the unbridled proliferation of crimes and corruption in the present day Annang land.

Keywords: *Mbiam, Corruption, Crime Control, Western Civilization, Annang Land.*

Introduction

For some time now, Nigerian society has been plagued with frightening crimes and more often than not the consequences are devastating and appalling. This crimes and corruption in Nigeria is very visible on every level from the intricate part of the government to the corner of the street (Oko, 2020:190). This unsavoury development has generated a lot of concern amongst the government, non-governmental organizations, and religious leaders. It is understood that crime is the act of violating the law and equally a social problem that transcends generations and mankind – and characterized all known contemporary modern societies. Hence, the focus of this work is not an exposition on crime, but to espouse on *Mbiam*

as a traditional means of crime control in pre-colonial Annang society. It is important to state categorically that before the advent of Western civilization and penal system to Africa and indeed Nigeria, traditional Annang society had means of social control, reformation and moral regulation which served then as instruments to correct and serve justice. Offiong (1991) asserts that these traditional methods of crime includes; *Mbiam* (oath), *Uwang* (tying of palm front), *Uyerenkang* (rubbing of charcoal). Thus, they were means the society used to encourage conformity to norms and values. To this end, the traditional methods of crime control, though primitive as it were, were very useful in the true sense of it, but as the society become more complex via industrialization and urbanization, the traditional institutions became increasingly disengaged from being the instruments of law and order, and the Western method of crime control was entrenched. In view of the fact that the western penal system which is now preferred to controlling crime has done little or nothing to addressing this societal hiatus, this work is principally geared toward x-raying how *Mbiam* as a traditional method of crime control was effectively administered to control crime until the adoption of the Western system (values) and the prospects of the integration of *Mbiam* into the western method of crime control in tackling the myriad of crime and corruption that have beleaguered the contemporary Annang society and thwarted its development efforts today.

Brief History of the Annang People

Essien (2020), rightly noted that in order to fully understand a people's practice, one needs to first understand who the people are. For Oko and Ogbodo (2022), cultural values of the people are their reputation. In line with this assertion, it will be expedient to examine briefly the history and culture of the Annang people as the necessary point of departure in order to understand their perception of the subject under consideration. It bears mentioning that the history of the Annang people in Nigeria has been a contentious topic due to the lack of precise historical narratives and written documents. Therefore, tracing the origin and migration of Annang people have been onerous, given the fact that only faint legends and memories of very fragmented oral traditions remains among the people concerning their origin and the various waves of migrations to their present abode. In spite of the wanton challenges confronting the tracing of Annang origin, Jefferey in his 1933 *Notes on the Ibibio Languages*, as cited by Essien (2010), espouses that Annang people have always been where they are found today. By implication, the Annang people have never migrated from anywhere.

However, applying the linguistic method, some scholars have differed from Jeffrey's position. For instance, taking the view of Udo into consideration, Udo (1983), strongly asserts that the Annang people are themselves a sub-group of the Ibibio who possesses the same culture and history of migration. Udo's position was predicated on the fact that the similarities that exist in every aspect are too much to be dismissed on grounds of long standing inter-group relationship. In his view, the notion of Annang as a different entity from the Ibibio was only for the aim of economic and political gains. Ukpong (2007), another scholar, argues that the Ibibio, including the Annang, all migrated from the Central Benue Valley through different routes to their different locations. Ineme and Udodata (2014), trace the ancestry of the Annang people to Bantu warriors and Zulu hunters in Central Africa, while their migratory patterns differ from that of the Ibibio stocks. This position shows that the Annang people are distinct from the Ibibio people. From the foregoing, it can be gleaned that there is no scholarly consensus regarding the origin and the migration of Annang people. The debates on tracing

the origin and migration pattern of the Annang people are not only peculiar to the Annang but also cuts across many other ethnic groups in Nigeria.

Geographically, the Annang territory in South Southern Nigeria is characterized by flat, low-lying landscapes and a humid climate. The people live within a rich forest zone, promoting palm wine tree growth and tropical vegetation. The Annang people are surrounded by Isogbo Igbo, Ngwa, Ndoki, and Ibibio. Their economic system is based on agricultural subsistence and exchange. They have a rich tradition in music, arts, and sculpture. Religion is central to their lives, with beliefs in a Supreme Deity (*Awasi Ibom*), intermediate deities, ancestors, and *Aruru* (spiritual forces). The Annang traditional society like other African societies functioned effectively because of the relevant system of social and judicial control that were evolved in administering its day to day affairs. These well-established institutions were used to enhance governance, regulate deviant behavior, enforced law and order which engendered peace and enhance the stability of the society. Ekanem, Essien and Okon (2022), identify these institutions to include *Ekpo, Ekpe, Ekong, Obon, Inam, Ebre, Ewana, Idiung, Ukang*, etc. *Mbiam* was also an important socio-judicial element used in checkmating crimes in traditional Annang society.

The Concept of Crime in Traditional Annang Society

Unlike the present western legal system in use in Nigeria today, what constituted crime in traditional Annang society was not codified. In short, Imo Benjamin Enoidem (Personal Communication on 17th October, 2023), notes that, any act or conduct that violated the cherished norms and values of the community or group, and was visited with severe sanction, can be referred to as a crime. According to him, a crime or an offence could be minor or serious depending on the circumstances. However, there were some major offences which amounted to serious crimes. These were referred to as “abominations”, due to their propensity to arouse strong indignation and condemnation among the people. Akpan Otu (Personal Communication on 29th October, 2023), observes that the most serious offences in traditional Annang society were also seen the same way in most other societies such as in the Ibibio and Oron societies. Furthermore, He explains that traditional crimes or offences, which were generally regarded as abominations, include murder, theft, adultery, rape, incest and suicide. He identified three major types of crimes in traditional Annang society as crimes against individuals, crimes against the community, and crimes against the gods or spirit world.

Crimes against individuals include assault, stealing of one’s property, murder and serious breaches of trust. In these crimes, the victims and their relatives took appropriate measures in seeking redress or revenge. Such measures often led to an endless cycle of problems and retaliations, including killings and counter killings, blood-feuds between families and communities, etc. Crimes against the community include acts of sabotage, like aiding and abetting enemies of the community, witchcraft, murder, adultery and incest, which were believed to bring about terrible consequences and woes to both the offender and the entire community. Crimes against the community also attracted severe punishment. Crimes against the gods or spirit world were actions and conducts that were believed to offend the gods and ancestors of the land, with serious consequences for the living. These include the desecration of sacred places and shrines, killing of sacred animals or totems associated with shrines, etc. Atanang, Ekanem and Oko (2022), espouse that crime of any sort is the stumbling block for peace economic growth of any community.

Thus, those who committed crimes against the gods and ancestors were either killed, ostracized, or banished from the community in order to placate the gods and ancestors so as to avoid a general evil vengeance being unleashed on the whole community by the offended forces in the spirit world. These sanctions remained in force until the offenders perform certain purification rites to appease the gods and ancestors. If these were not done, any misfortune in the family or community would be attributed to the anger of the gods and the spirit world against the actions of the offenders. Umanah (2001), in his own observation, notes that certain crimes such as murder, theft and adultery were crimes against God, community as well as against man. The Annang people, in his view, hold that in committing such crimes, a man was acting contrary to the will of God.

Concept and Constituents of *Mbiam*

Mbiam has been variously and differently conceptualized by scholars. For instance, Udoh (2008), submits that *Mbiam* is an oath that may be either a solemn declaration of an intention to either do or not do a thing. Hence, it is a solemn promise made that is binding by an oath which may be either verbal formula or a symbolic action. Such an action or formula is recognized by both parties as formal act which binds the people (actors) to fulfill their promises. Equally, *Mbiam* as an oath may also be seen as a bond or agreement entered into between persons or groups of persons or between a group of men and a god or gods. According to Offiong (1991), *Mbiam* is conceptualized as a magically potent object used in swearing oaths and in fortifying one's property against thieves which has the supernatural ability to detect the innocent and the guilty as well as to punish the offender. The three main ways in which *Mbiam* was used included property fortification, settlement of disputes and determination of innocence and guilt with respect to crimes. Hence, it was believed to be capable of discriminating between the innocent and the offender.

Ukpong (2007) refers to *Mbiam* as any object used for personal protection for the guarding of personal property or for swearing. In his perspective, *Mbiam* is comparable to the swearing on a Holy Bible. It is believed to have the power of detecting culprits and punishing them accordingly, unless the curse was removed. Consequently, *Mbiam* usually take various forms. It could be liquid, sacred drum, certain leaves, human blood or animal/human parts, etc. In fact, anything or object believed by the people to be sacred was used as *Mbiam*. It can be taken by an individual as invocation to a deity to witness that a statement made by the individual on a disputed issue is true. *Mbiam* itself may consist merely of swearing by the name of some feared dangerous deity (such as *Iso Itiat* in Akuku Udim- Ikpe, Etim Ekpo) or ancestor believed to be capable of punishing those who swear falsely by it, or it may consist of some concoction specially prepared by a traditional medicine man or woman into which he/she invoked the name of one or more dangerous deities (Ekong, 1983). According to Essien (2005), an accused person was asked to swear on *Mbiam* to declare himself or herself innocent of a crime, and it was believed that the accused would not tell lies and get away without being killed after swearing on it. As reported by Udo (1983), a typical administration of *Mbiam* (oath) usually take this form with precise utterances: If I have done, or if I do or if I will do such and such, this *Mbiam* kill me, if not so, *Mbiam* protect and bless me and my whole house this and next generation and forever. Essien (2010) and Antia (2005), agree that the Annang believed that if one lied, the power of *Mbiam* would kill such an individual.

The Relevance of *Mbiam* in Crime Control in Traditional Annang Society

Mbiam, a traditional practice in Annang land, was recognized as a veritable means of crime control in the community. This practice involves the use of spiritual and cultural beliefs to deter individuals from engaging in criminal activities. The effectiveness of *Mbiam* as a crime control mechanism lies in its ability to instill fear and respect for traditional values and norms. In pre-colonial Annang land, *Mbiam* provided the norms and standards of behaviour for the people and checked criminal activities on the part of the people and the rulers as it guaranteed the existence and enforcement of the traditional law, morality and ethics. According to Akpan (2018), *Mbiam* served as a form of social control in Annang society, where individuals are held accountable for their deeds and misdeeds through spiritual consequences.

Ekong (2015), notes that in traditional Annang society, the practice of *Mbiam* was utilized as a means of discovering theft within the community. *Mbiam* was a spiritual practice that involved invoking the spirits to reveal or establish the culprit of a particular crime and prescribe the appropriate punishment. The process typically involved the use of divination tools such as palm nuts or cowry shells, as well as the guidance of a skilled diviner (*Abia Idiung*) who could interpret the messages from the spirits. In Ekong's view, when a theft occurred in the community, the *Abia Idiung* would be called upon to conduct *Mbiam* session to determine the identity of the thief. The diviner would lead the process, asking questions and interpreting the responses from the spirits to identify the guilty party. Once the culprit was identified, the *Abia Idiung* would then decide on the appropriate punishment, which could range from restitution to public shaming or even banishment from the community.

Similarly, Akpan (2015), notes that *Mbiam* was a form of social control that was used to regulate the behavior of traditional rulers and ensure that they acted in accordance with the expectations of the community. Traditional rulers were expected to lead by example and uphold the values of honesty, integrity, and respect for others. Failure to do so could result in the imposition of sanctions by the community, such as ostracism or removal from office. Hence, by swearing *Mbiam* oath, the traditional rulers subjected themselves to the scrutiny of the community, the ancestors and *Awasi Ibom* (God), if they fail to dispense justice without fear and favour. This practice was essential in maintaining order and harmony within the society, as well as upholding the values and traditions of the Annang people. Also, *Mbiam* served as a form of social control in traditional Annang society, where the spiritual realms were engaged to ensure that justice was served and harmony was maintained within the community.

Therefore, the fear of spiritual retribution serves as a powerful tool in preventing crime and maintaining social order within the community. In other words, the fear and belief in *Mbiam* helped the people to maintain high moral standard and strengthened cordial relationship between God (Supreme Being, *Awasi Ibom*) and man as well as between humans. *Mbiam* provided checks and balances which regulates and put the Annang community on a steady economic, political, social, cultural and religious balance responsible for stability and meaningful government. As noted by Imo Benjamin (Personal Communication on 6th October, 2024), a mere mentioning of the word *Mbiam* in traditional Annang society evoked awe and automatically called the people to order and directed their actions. As pointed out by Essien (2005), *Mbiam* was and is still one form of traditional instrument of crime control in Annang land administered through the use of metaphysical or mystical powers to discover hidden

secrets. *Mbiam* is feared much in Annang locality and this fear has contributed immensely to crime control. Antia (2005), notes that all those who committed the most serious crimes of adultery, rape, elopement, stealing, abortion, the profanation of the most sacred traditions, (the eating of new yams before the official celebration of the New Year festival) and murder were given adequate penalties.

In addition, *Mbiam* prevents wicked acts among the people because no matter how secret a particular crime is, it must be discovered and the defaulter or culprit would be punished according to the laws of the land. Therefore, the fear of *Mbiam* was the driving force in the maintenance of a high level of morality by doing what is right, good and moral and avoiding what is evil, wrong and bad. In view of the above, Essien (2020) notes that avoidance of crimes as well as the maintenance of law in among the pre-colonial Annang society was not really acts rendered by individuals from their freewill and love which they had for their community, rather their actions were instigated by fear of immediate retribution. *Mbiam*, therefore, was and still is a potent instrument of social control. *Mbiam* is an effective traditional instrument used by the people to discover the truth of a matter, discover hidden secrets and to cast away doubt with reference to the validity and reliability of a statement or accusation in any circumstances. However, according to Ekong (2009), because of the awe it creates in the minds of the people, many people in Annang land have shunned or avoided embarking on any criminal activity. Unfortunately, this aged-long traditional has been seriously challenged in the contemporary time due to the proliferating influence of Western culture and civilization.

Western Influence on the Practice of *Mbiam* in the Contemporary Annang Society

Like other African communities, the Annang traditional society was able to run its daily operations with an efficient set of governmental institutions that had been developed over time. To improve governance, the people made use of some well-established social and judicial institutions. The institutions upheld law and order, which promoted stability and harmony in the community. Among these institutes was the *Mbiam* institution. Astonishingly, the social life of the Annang people started to feel the pressure of modernization during the colonial era and the subsequent spread of foreign or Western influence. The foreign influence acts as a catalyst, creating room for a rapid process of social change. For instance, the introduction of Western legal systems and institutions in traditional Annang society strongly affected the relevance of *Mbiam*. With the colonization of Nigeria by the British, Western legal norms and practices were imposed on the indigenous population, leading to a shift in the way justice was administered. This had a direct impact on the institution of *Mbiam*, as the people embrace elements of Western law and procedure. Western culture also condemned traditional method of crime control embedded in *Mbiam* and exalted the modern legal/judicial institution such as the court; police, etc. It bears mentioning that the existence of police and courts has not completely eroded the power vested in *Mbiam*, the people still use it as a quick measure in uncovering secret criminal acts.

Furthermore, Western education and modernity became veritable social factors disrupting many aspects of traditional institutions in Annang charged with the sole responsibility of controlling crime such as the institution of *Mbiam*. With the introduction of Western education, the values and beliefs of the Annang people began to change, leading to a shift in attitudes towards crime and punishment. This, in turn, affected the way the *Mbiam* system is perceived and utilized as a tool for crime control today. Furthermore, as Western culture

became more prevalent in the region, traditional customs and beliefs began to erode, leading to a decline in the effectiveness of the traditional institutions as a means of crime control. This cultural shift has had a lasting impact on the institution of *Mbiam* and its role in maintaining social order in Annang land. Therefore, the influence of Western civilization, culture, and education on the institution of *Mbiam* as an instrument of crime control in traditional Annang land has been significant. The introduction of Western legal systems, education, and cultural values has led to changes in the way justice is administered and perceived in the Annang community. These influences have shaped the evolution of *Mbiam* and its role in maintaining social order in Annang land.

The Need for Incorporation of *Mbiam* into the Western System of Crime Control Today

Despite the entrenchment of Western system of crime control and public governance in Annang land, vices such as political corruption, kidnapping, armed robbery, etc, have become very prevalent in the society, quite unlike what was obtainable in the Annang traditional society. The failure of the western system of crime control to effectively regulate the increasing crime rates calls for the integration of *Mbiam* into western approaches for enhanced effectiveness. The integration of *Mbiam* into modern approaches to crime control has the potential to significantly improve the effectiveness of the justice system. In many cases, innocent individuals are wrongfully arrested and convicted for crimes they did not commit, while the true culprits remain at large due to weaknesses in the Western system of crime control. By incorporating *Mbiam* into the process, the identification and punishment of the real perpetrators can be more accurately and efficiently achieved.

The integration of *Mbiam* into the western methods of crime control will instill fear of immediate consequences of breaking the *Mbiam* oath, which will serve as a strong deterrent, ensuring that individuals adhere to societal norms and values. One of the key reasons for the ineffectiveness of western crime control methods in Annang land is the lack of fear of consequences among individuals who engage in criminal activities. Politicians, for example, may make promises during their campaigns but fail to fulfill them once in office without facing any immediate repercussions. This lack of accountability contributes to the prevalence of political corruption and other social vices in the society. By integrating *Mbiam* into western approaches to crime control, individuals, including politicians who swear via *Mbiam* oath, will be more inclined to uphold their promises and act in the best interest of the society. The fear of facing the consequences of breaking the *Mbiam* oath will serve as a powerful deterrent, ensuring that people adhere to ethical standards and societal norms.

Conclusion

It is evident that Annang society has evolved dramatically. Many people live in both urban and rural areas, have access to power, and use a range of communication devices. Equally, the spread of Western civilization has directly impinged on the existing socio-judicial institutions such as *Mbiam*, exalting the western method of crime control such as the police, army, court, and other agencies in Annang land and other places in Nigeria. This is strikingly antithetical to the traditional Annang society where *Mbiam* served as a veritable tool of crime control. Unfortunately, the entrenchment of western system of crime control has not significantly addressed vices-like corruption, kidnapping, armed robbery, etc. The unbridled escalation of these crimes in Annang land despite the prevalence of western methods of crime control highlights the need for the integration of *Mbiam* into contemporary or Western approaches.

Hence, a combination of the strengths of both systems in the modern day Annang society will effectively regulate criminal activities, promote accountability, and foster peace and harmony in Annang land. Oko and Ndubuwa (2022), support this view when they said that societal peace is possible with maintenance of covenant with God and preservation of the environment.

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